

Open Source Computational Tool in Python for Cardiac Variability Analysis in Biomedical Research

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Abstract

The present study introduces ECGRats, a Python-based tool with a graphical user interface developed using the open-source Kivy framework, designed to facilitate the analysis of heart rate variability (HRV) in rodent ECGs. The software integrates preprocessing algorithms, including baseline correction, band-pass and notch filtering, and stationary wavelet transform, to accurately detect QRS complexes and R peaks, enabling calculation of RR intervals and HRV parameters. ECGRats features an interactive interface with screens for system configuration, data visualization, HRV calculation, and statistical analysis, including histograms and Poincaré plots, which provide complementary insights into heart rhythm patterns. The tool was validated using ECG recordings from Wistar rats, demonstrating high accuracy in detecting global HRV metrics, particularly HR, Average NN, SDNN, and rMSSD. Event-count-based parameters (NN20, pNN20, NN6, pNN6) showed greater variability, highlighting the influence of signal noise and limited reference data for rodents. Overall, ECGRats offers a reproducible, and accessible solution for preclinical research, supporting both short-term and global HRV assessments. By integrating statistical and graphical analyses, the tool can aid in understanding autonomic nervous system regulation, providing a foundation for studies on cardiovascular physiology and pharmacological interventions in rodent models. ECGRats is freely available on Zenodo as an open-access resource.

Keywords: Heart rate variability; Computational tool; Rats; Electrocardiogram.

Highlights:

- Objective: To evaluate the reliability of the ECGRats tool for HRV in rodents;

- Methodology: Extraction and analysis of HRV parameters from ECG of Wistar rats;
- Data and tests: Statistical analysis comparing temporal and spectral metrics of HRV;
- Results: High accuracy in detecting R peaks and calculating NN intervals;
- Applications: Potential for studies involving nervous systems in animal models;

1. Introduction

In the human body, the cardiovascular system is responsible for fluid transport, driven by cardiac cycles of contraction and relaxation initiated by the depolarization of cardiac cells [1][2]. At rest, these cells are polarized, and when they depolarize, they trigger a charge inversion that propagates in a cascade effect until it encompasses the entire heart [3], generating the electrical activity that sustains its function [4].

Capturing this electrical activity is essential for understanding cardiac function. In this context, the need for automatic tools to process such information has been increasing [5]. One example is the electrocardiogram (ECG), a low-cost, easy-to-use device that is widely employed to monitor the electrical activity of the heart [6][7].

Automatic ECG analysis makes it possible to rapidly assess many exams, eliminating the need for manual annotations by physicians or researchers [5]. This approach is useful not only in hospitals but also in experimental studies with animals, such as rats, which are widely used in disease research and drug testing [8].

In rodent studies, automatic heart rate variability (HRV) analysis enables the evaluation of the cardiac response to different conditions, such as drug administration or the presence of pathologies [9][10]. Furthermore, tracking these data over time allows for the identification of relevant patterns and effects [9][10].

The analysis process begins with the identification of the main components of the ECG trace, P waves, QRS complexes, and T waves [7][11], followed by the detection of R peaks. From these, HRV is calculated, reflecting the heart's ability to adapt to physiological changes [12].

These calculations are based on the time series of NN (or RR) intervals, which correspond to the time between consecutive beats, from which several parameters of interest are derived. Among them, heart rate (HR) provides a global measure of cardiac rhythm, while the average NN interval (Average) serves as a baseline for evaluating other metrics [13].

SDNN (Standard Deviation of NN intervals) represents the standard deviation of all NN intervals and is widely used as a global indicator of variability, as it integrates the combined action of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems [13]. rMSSD (Root Mean Square of Successive Differences) expresses the square root of the mean of the squared differences between adjacent NN intervals, being sensitive to rapid changes in heart rate and considered a robust marker of short-term parasympathetic activity [14].

Parameters such as NN20 and pNN20 quantify the absolute number and the proportion of NN interval pairs differing by more than 20 milliseconds. These reflect vagal modulation but are more susceptible to noise and non-physiological variations, particularly in short recordings. For rodent studies, NN6 and pNN6 can also be used, following the same rationale but adapting the threshold to 6 milliseconds, given the higher heart rate of these animals [13].

In this work, we present the graphical user interface (GUI) ECGRats, developed in Python with a framework for GUI development. The tool integrates preprocessing algorithms and HRV index calculations such as SDNN, rMSSD, NN20, and pNN20, focusing on applications in rodent research. The software is freely available on Zenodo, an open-access digital repository maintained by the European Commission and CERN to share scientific publications, datasets, and software, as an open-source resource [15].

Thus, the main objective of this work is to provide an open-source, fully documented computational tool that facilitates HRV analysis in rodent studies. By bringing together validated algorithms adapted for this experimental context, ECGRats aims not only to speed up and standardize ECG processing but also to contribute to the reproducibility and comparability of results in biomedical research. This initiative is expected to support both basic investigations and preclinical studies, expanding opportunities to explore physiological parameters and strengthening the knowledge base on cardiovascular function in animal models.

2. Methods

The tool was implemented in Python, with a graphical interface built in the open-source framework Kivy, which enables the development of interactive and responsive applications, compatible with multiple platforms, including desktop and web environments.

2.1 Processing of the raw ECG signal

The preprocessing of the ECG signal included the application of techniques for baseline removal, which corrects slow oscillations caused by animal movements or respiratory variations, a band-pass filter (high and low), and a notch filter to attenuate interferences, in addition to a method for correcting the electrical baseline that restores the tracing to the reference level, facilitating subsequent analyses (Fig. 1).

For QRS complex detection, the input signal is initially filtered by a band-pass (0.5 Hz to 100 Hz) to reduce high-frequency noise, baseline drift, attenuate P and T waves, and enhance QRS complexes while preserving Q and S. Next, the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) without phase shift is applied, using the Haar wavelet [16]. The detail coefficients (SWDN) of the SWT are computed at the level covering frequencies close to 50 Hz, the range where relevant spectral components of the QRS complex are concentrated for proper delineation.

To identify the intervals containing QRS complexes, an adaptive thresholding approach is employed, where the threshold value is adjusted according to moving time windows applied to the SWDN coefficients and signal-dependent statistical measures. Among all solution sets obtained with different thresholds, a voting algorithm automatically selects the most consistent solution. R-peak annotation is then performed at the position of maximum amplitude within the detected QRS interval. After marking all R-peaks throughout the recording, RR intervals are calculated and used as the basis for the extraction of HRV parameters.

Fig. 1. A possible pipeline for processing an ECG signal with ECGRats. After preprocessing, peak detection and cardiac variability calculation are performed. The arrows pointing inside the box determine the input parameters, and the arrows pointing outwards, the output parameters, respectively.

2.2 Requirements Engineering

Initially, a software requirements analysis was conducted, considering the needs of the users in this field. Based on this analysis, the requirements were documented, including their origin, priority, and possible dependencies. Finally, validation was carried out through screen prototyping (Fig. 2). The first screen was designed to be the tool's home screen, the second corresponds to system configuration, the third screen displays the data plot and heart rate variability calculations, and the fourth screen presents the statistical analysis.

Fig. 2. Prototype of the proposed tool interface: home screen, system configuration screen, data visualization and heart rate variability analysis, and statistical analysis.

2.3 Tool Validation

For tool validation, ECG signals from Wistar rats, provided by the University of Parma, Italy [17], were used. In this study, cardiac electrical activity was recorded through electrocardiograms captured by platform receivers (RPC-1, Data Sciences International), placed under the animal cages, and acquired using the ART-Gold 4.2 system (Data Sciences International), with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz.

Electrocardiographic recordings were conducted for 1 hour during the dark (active) phase of the light-dark cycle, between 10 a.m. and 11 a.m., on different days. From the complete dataset, ECG signals were segmented into smaller parts, totaling 100 recordings of approximately 6 minutes each, organized into groups of ten recordings per animal. All signals were processed using the tool developed in this work.

The results obtained were then compared with reference values described in the literature, considering classical HRV parameters in rodents. The evaluated metrics include heart rate, mean NN intervals, SDNN, rMSSD, as well as NN20 and NN6 counts, and their respective proportions pNN20 and pNN6.

To complement the analysis, a statistical evaluation of the data was performed using Jamovi software, which included the calculation of the coefficient of variation (CV%) to assess the proximity of individual results from each rat, as well as the standard deviation

to measure data dispersion. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test was also applied to verify the distribution of the data.

3. Results and discussion

The tool was developed in Python, with a graphical interface built using the Kivy framework. The structure of the screens was designed to facilitate signal loading, algorithm execution, and interactive visualization of the results.

During signal processing (Fig. 3), the application of filters improved the quality of the electrocardiographic tracing. Initially, a band-pass filter was applied to attenuate low- and high-frequency noise, such as muscular interference, preserving the relevant cardiac signal range. Next, a notch filter was applied to eliminate 50 Hz electrical interference from the power supply. Finally, baseline correction was performed, returning the tracing to the reference level and facilitating subsequent analyses. With this processing, the algorithm was able to identify R-peaks, essential for the calculation of heart rate variability parameters.

Fig. 3. Electrocardiographic signal processing flow, including application of filters to attenuate low and high frequency noise, removal of electrical interference and baseline correction, aiming to optimize the detection of the QRS complex and, subsequently, of the R peaks.

The first screen presents the tool named ECGRats, which offers the option to select either blood pressure or electrocardiogram analysis. The functionality described in this article refers to the electrocardiogram module, while the blood pressure measurement in

rats is addressed in a separate publication [18]. The second screen corresponds to system configuration, allowing the user to define parameters such as the sampling rate, high-pass and low-pass filters, and the notch filter. Additionally, a button is available to select an Excel file containing pre-collected rat ECG data.

Third screen generates the data plot, allowing visualization of raw signals, filtered signals, and R-peak annotations. Below the plot, heart rate variability calculations are displayed, including HR, mean NN intervals, SDNN, rMSSD, NN20, NN6, pNN20, and pNN6. Finally, the fourth screen presents statistical analysis through two plots: the Poincaré diagram and the histogram, providing a detailed view of heart rate variability patterns (Fig. 4).

The Poincaré diagram allowed evaluation of dispersion and correlation between consecutive cardiac intervals, providing visual information on rhythm regularity or irregularity and patterns associated with different physiological conditions [19]. The histogram highlighted the distribution of NN intervals, enabling identification of normality or asymmetry and the frequency of specific values, aiding in the detection of potential changes in cardiac behavior [19].

Fig. 4. Interface of the ECGRats computerized tool: (A) Home screen; (B) screen for file selection and parameter configuration; (C) results display; and (D) final statistical analysis screen.

All signals were processed using the tool, and the results were compared with reference values reported in the literature (Fig. 5). HR had 97.3% of values within the expected range, indicating effective R-peak detection and consistent RR interval calculation. The mean NN intervals showed 100% compliance, demonstrating accuracy in the average beat calculation.

Among HRV parameters, SDNN reflects the combined action of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. High SDNN values generally indicate better autonomic balance and a healthier physiological state [13,20]. In this study, SDNN showed 61.8% of values within the reference range, suggesting possible influence from factors such as signal noise, sample size, and individual biological variability of the animals.

Conversely, rMSSD showed high compliance, with 99.1% of values within the reference range. This parameter is a marker of vagal function [14,21]. Being sensitive to rapid heart rate fluctuations, rMSSD primarily reflects short-term parasympathetic activity [22,23]. Its adherence to the expected range suggests the tool's capacity to detect vagal modulation in rats.

On the other hand, NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 quantify the relative frequency of variations above certain thresholds between successive NN intervals. In this study, these parameters showed low adherence to reference values, with less than 20% of data within established limits. For example, NN20 counts the number of NN interval pairs whose absolute difference exceeds 20 ms and, like rMSSD, is related to parasympathetic activity [24]. However, this index is more susceptible to noise or rapid non-physiological variations [25].

Regarding NN20 and NN6 parameters, it is important to note that literature still lacks well-established reference values for rodents [25]. This gap makes direct comparisons difficult and highlights the need for further studies to better understand the physiology of these indicators in animal models. Moreover, as these metrics are relatively recent in the context of experimental rodent ECGs, there is room for further standardization and validation [26,27].

Fig. 5. Result of the distribution of values by reference range (%) obtained from rat ECG samples.

Statistical analysis of the parameters calculated by the tool for Wistar rats revealed differences in stability among the evaluated metrics (Table 1). Global parameters such as HR (mean = 403.23 bpm; standard deviation = 16.9 bpm; CV = 4.20%) and Average NN (mean = 148.96 ms; standard deviation = 6.5 ms; CV = 4.36%) showed low relative variability, indicating high consistency and closeness of recorded values.

In contrast, SDNN (mean = 2.35 ms; standard deviation = 0.717 ms; CV = 30.55%) and rMSSD (mean = 3.18 ms; standard deviation = 0.896 ms; CV = 28.17%) exhibited moderate variability, suggesting more noticeable fluctuations, but still within an acceptable stability range.

Event-based metrics such as NN20 (mean = 1.30; CV = 125.88%), pNN20 (mean = 0.175; CV = 130.34%), NN6 (mean = 24.00; CV = 108.03%), and pNN6 (mean = 3.23; CV = 115.47%) showed high relative variability, indicating marked fluctuations across different recording times. This instability may reflect rapid physiological variations as well as increased sensitivity to signal noise and artifacts.

The Shapiro-Wilk normality test indicated p-values above 0.05 for HR, Average NN, SDNN, and rMSSD, suggesting compatibility with a normal distribution. On the other hand, NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 metrics had p-values below 0.05, indicating rejection of the normality hypothesis and reinforcing the need for caution when applying parametric statistical tests to these data.

Table 1

Statistical analysis of HRV parameters from rat ECG samples, including mean, standard deviation, p-value from Shapiro-Wilk test, and coefficient of variation (CV%).

											Mean	Standard Deviation	P Shapiro-Wilk	CV(%)
HR	386.43	368.23	399.48	415.1	413.02	421.88	407.29	422.92	403.12	394.79	403	16.9	0.537	4.2
Average NN	155.14	162.86	150.36	144.53	144.9	142.14	147.28	141.71	148.75	151.96	149	6.5	0.378	4.36
SDNN	2.14	3.45	3.51	2.77	1.37	1.62	2.36	1.92	1.94	2.38	2.35	0.717	0.459	30.55
rMSSD	3.26	5.07	4.08	3.28	2.01	2.12	3.06	2.69	2.93	3.29	3.18	0.896	0.373	28.17
NN20	0	5	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	1.3	1.64	0.005	125.88
pNN20	0	0.71	0.26	0.26	0	0	0.26	0	0	0.26	0.175	0.228	0.003	130.34
NN6	26	95	18	7	5	11	16	22	25	15	24	25.9	<0.001	108.03
pNN6	3.54	13.51	2.38	0.9	0.64	1.36	2.05	2.72	3.24	1.98	3.23	3.73	<0.001	115.47

Overall, the findings indicate that the ECGRats tool shows potential for applications in rodent ECG research, particularly when focusing on global and short-term HRV metrics. The discrepancies observed in event-based parameters highlight the need for ongoing tool refinement and the expansion of reference datasets for animal studies. Considering that heart rate variability is related to autonomic modulation, the tool may also be useful in investigations indirectly exploring sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system function, although this hypothesis requires validation in specific studies.

4. Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that the ECGRats tool provides consistent performance in the analysis of rodent ECGs, particularly for global and short-term HRV metrics, showing promise as a resource for preclinical research.

Among its strengths, the tool integrates statistical calculations and graphical representations, such as histograms and Poincaré diagrams, which offer complementary insights into HRV patterns and can aid in data interpretation. Despite these advances, some limitations were identified, including discrepancies observed in the NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 parameters, as well as the lack of reference values for these indices in rodents.

For future perspectives, it is proposed to refine the algorithm and expand the database with different experimental rodent profiles. Additionally, considering that HRV reflects aspects of autonomic modulation, the tool could be applied in studies aimed at understanding interactions between the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Mariana da Palma Valério: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Terigi Augusto Scardovelli: Methodology, Software, Validation.

Vlasta Bari: Visualization.

Pietra Aguiar dos Reis: Writing – original draft.

Silvia Becker: Software.

Axel Loewe: Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

Silvia Cristina Martini: Data curation.

Silvia Regina Matos da Silva Boschi: Visualization, Investigation.

Tabajara de Oliveira Gonzalez: Writing – review and editing.

Alessandro Pereira da Silva: Writing – original draft, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The preprocessing of the ECG signal included the application of techniques for baseline removal, which corrects slow oscillations caused by animal movements or respiratory variations, a band-pass filter (high and low), and a notch filter to attenuate interferences, in addition to a method for correcting the electrical baseline that restores the tracing to the reference level, facilitating subsequent analyses (Fig. 1).

For QRS complex detection, the input signal is initially filtered by a band-pass (0.5 Hz to 100 Hz) to reduce high-frequency noise, baseline drift, attenuate P and T waves, and enhance QRS complexes while preserving Q and S. Next, the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT) without phase shift is applied, using the Haar wavelet [16]. The detail coefficients (SWDN) of the SWT are computed at the level covering frequencies close to 50 Hz, the range where relevant spectral components of the QRS complex are concentrated for proper delineation.

To identify the intervals containing QRS complexes, an adaptive thresholding approach is employed, where the threshold value is adjusted according to moving time windows applied to the SWDN coefficients and signal-dependent statistical measures. Among all solution sets obtained with different thresholds, a voting algorithm automatically selects the most consistent solution. R-peak annotation is then performed at the position of maximum amplitude within the detected QRS interval. After marking all R-peaks throughout the recording, RR intervals are calculated and used as the basis for the extraction of HRV parameters.

Fig. 1. A possible pipeline for processing an ECG signal with ECGRats. After preprocessing, peak detection and cardiac variability calculation are performed. The arrows pointing inside the box determine the input parameters, and the arrows pointing outwards, the output parameters, respectively.

2.2 Requirements Engineering

Initially, a software requirements analysis was conducted, considering the needs of the users in this field. Based on this analysis, the requirements were documented, including their origin, priority, and possible dependencies. Finally, validation was carried out through screen prototyping (Fig. 2). The first screen was designed to be the tool's home screen, the second corresponds to system configuration, the third screen displays the data plot and heart rate variability calculations, and the fourth screen presents the statistical analysis.

Fig. 2. Prototype of the proposed tool interface: home screen, system configuration screen, data visualization and heart rate variability analysis, and statistical analysis.

2.3 Tool Validation

For tool validation, ECG signals from Wistar rats, provided by the University of Parma, Italy [17], were used. In this study, cardiac electrical activity was recorded through electrocardiograms captured by platform receivers (RPC-1, Data Sciences International), placed under the animal cages, and acquired using the ART-Gold 4.2 system (Data Sciences International), with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz.

Electrocardiographic recordings were conducted for 1 hour during the dark (active) phase of the light-dark cycle, between 10 a.m. and 11 a.m., on different days. From the complete dataset, ECG signals were segmented into smaller parts, totaling 100 recordings of approximately 6 minutes each, organized into groups of ten recordings per animal. All signals were processed using the tool developed in this work.

The results obtained were then compared with reference values described in the literature, considering classical HRV parameters in rodents. The evaluated metrics include heart rate, mean NN intervals, SDNN, rMSSD, as well as NN20 and NN6 counts, and their respective proportions pNN20 and pNN6.

To complement the analysis, a statistical evaluation of the data was performed using Jamovi software, which included the calculation of the coefficient of variation (CV%) to assess the proximity of individual results from each rat, as well as the standard deviation

to measure data dispersion. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test was also applied to verify the distribution of the data.

3. Results and discussion

The tool was developed in Python, with a graphical interface built using the Kivy framework. The structure of the screens was designed to facilitate signal loading, algorithm execution, and interactive visualization of the results.

During signal processing (Fig. 3), the application of filters improved the quality of the electrocardiographic tracing. Initially, a band-pass filter was applied to attenuate low- and high-frequency noise, such as muscular interference, preserving the relevant cardiac signal range. Next, a notch filter was applied to eliminate 50 Hz electrical interference from the power supply. Finally, baseline correction was performed, returning the tracing to the reference level and facilitating subsequent analyses. With this processing, the algorithm was able to identify R-peaks, essential for the calculation of heart rate variability parameters.

Fig. 3. Electrocardiographic signal processing flow, including application of filters to attenuate low and high frequency noise, removal of electrical interference and baseline correction, aiming to optimize the detection of the QRS complex and, subsequently, of the R peaks.

The first screen presents the tool named ECGRats, which offers the option to select either blood pressure or electrocardiogram analysis. The functionality described in this article refers to the electrocardiogram module, while the blood pressure measurement in

rats is addressed in a separate publication [18]. The second screen corresponds to system configuration, allowing the user to define parameters such as the sampling rate, high-pass and low-pass filters, and the notch filter. Additionally, a button is available to select an Excel file containing pre-collected rat ECG data.

Third screen generates the data plot, allowing visualization of raw signals, filtered signals, and R-peak annotations. Below the plot, heart rate variability calculations are displayed, including HR, mean NN intervals, SDNN, rMSSD, NN20, NN6, pNN20, and pNN6. Finally, the fourth screen presents statistical analysis through two plots: the Poincaré diagram and the histogram, providing a detailed view of heart rate variability patterns (Fig. 4).

The Poincaré diagram allowed evaluation of dispersion and correlation between consecutive cardiac intervals, providing visual information on rhythm regularity or irregularity and patterns associated with different physiological conditions [19]. The histogram highlighted the distribution of NN intervals, enabling identification of normality or asymmetry and the frequency of specific values, aiding in the detection of potential changes in cardiac behavior [19].

Fig. 4. Interface of the ECGRats computerized tool: (A) Home screen; (B) screen for file selection and parameter configuration; (C) results display; and (D) final statistical analysis screen.

All signals were processed using the tool, and the results were compared with reference values reported in the literature (Fig. 5). HR had 97.3% of values within the expected range, indicating effective R-peak detection and consistent RR interval calculation. The mean NN intervals showed 100% compliance, demonstrating accuracy in the average beat calculation.

Among HRV parameters, SDNN reflects the combined action of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. High SDNN values generally indicate better autonomic balance and a healthier physiological state [13,20]. In this study, SDNN showed 61.8% of values within the reference range, suggesting possible influence from factors such as signal noise, sample size, and individual biological variability of the animals.

Conversely, rMSSD showed high compliance, with 99.1% of values within the reference range. This parameter is a marker of vagal function [14,21]. Being sensitive to rapid heart rate fluctuations, rMSSD primarily reflects short-term parasympathetic activity [22,23]. Its adherence to the expected range suggests the tool's capacity to detect vagal modulation in rats.

On the other hand, NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 quantify the relative frequency of variations above certain thresholds between successive NN intervals. In this study, these parameters showed low adherence to reference values, with less than 20% of data within established limits. For example, NN20 counts the number of NN interval pairs whose absolute difference exceeds 20 ms and, like rMSSD, is related to parasympathetic activity [24]. However, this index is more susceptible to noise or rapid non-physiological variations [25].

Regarding NN20 and NN6 parameters, it is important to note that literature still lacks well-established reference values for rodents [25]. This gap makes direct comparisons difficult and highlights the need for further studies to better understand the physiology of these indicators in animal models. Moreover, as these metrics are relatively recent in the context of experimental rodent ECGs, there is room for further standardization and validation [26,27].

Fig. 5. Result of the distribution of values by reference range (%) obtained from rat ECG samples.

Statistical analysis of the parameters calculated by the tool for Wistar rats revealed differences in stability among the evaluated metrics (Table 1). Global parameters such as HR (mean = 403.23 bpm; standard deviation = 16.9 bpm; CV = 4.20%) and Average NN (mean = 148.96 ms; standard deviation = 6.5 ms; CV = 4.36%) showed low relative variability, indicating high consistency and closeness of recorded values.

In contrast, SDNN (mean = 2.35 ms; standard deviation = 0.717 ms; CV = 30.55%) and rMSSD (mean = 3.18 ms; standard deviation = 0.896 ms; CV = 28.17%) exhibited moderate variability, suggesting more noticeable fluctuations, but still within an acceptable stability range.

Event-based metrics such as NN20 (mean = 1.30; CV = 125.88%), pNN20 (mean = 0.175; CV = 130.34%), NN6 (mean = 24.00; CV = 108.03%), and pNN6 (mean = 3.23; CV = 115.47%) showed high relative variability, indicating marked fluctuations across different recording times. This instability may reflect rapid physiological variations as well as increased sensitivity to signal noise and artifacts.

The Shapiro-Wilk normality test indicated p-values above 0.05 for HR, Average NN, SDNN, and rMSSD, suggesting compatibility with a normal distribution. On the other hand, NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 metrics had p-values below 0.05, indicating rejection of the normality hypothesis and reinforcing the need for caution when applying parametric statistical tests to these data.

Table 1

Statistical analysis of HRV parameters from rat ECG samples, including mean, standard deviation, p-value from Shapiro-Wilk test, and coefficient of variation (CV%).

											Mean	Standard Deviation	P Shapiro-Wilk	CV(%)
HR	386.43	368.23	399.48	415.1	413.02	421.88	407.29	422.92	403.12	394.79	403	16.9	0.537	4.2
Average NN	155.14	162.86	150.36	144.53	144.9	142.14	147.28	141.71	148.75	151.96	149	6.5	0.378	4.36
SDNN	2.14	3.45	3.51	2.77	1.37	1.62	2.36	1.92	1.94	2.38	2.35	0.717	0.459	30.55
rMSSD	3.26	5.07	4.08	3.28	2.01	2.12	3.06	2.69	2.93	3.29	3.18	0.896	0.373	28.17
NN20	0	5	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	1.3	1.64	0.005	125.88
pNN20	0	0.71	0.26	0.26	0	0	0.26	0	0	0.26	0.175	0.228	0.003	130.34
NN6	26	95	18	7	5	11	16	22	25	15	24	25.9	<0.001	108.03
pNN6	3.54	13.51	2.38	0.9	0.64	1.36	2.05	2.72	3.24	1.98	3.23	3.73	<0.001	115.47

Overall, the findings indicate that the ECGRats tool shows potential for applications in rodent ECG research, particularly when focusing on global and short-term HRV metrics. The discrepancies observed in event-based parameters highlight the need for ongoing tool refinement and the expansion of reference datasets for animal studies. Considering that heart rate variability is related to autonomic modulation, the tool may also be useful in investigations indirectly exploring sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system function, although this hypothesis requires validation in specific studies.

4. Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that the ECGRats tool provides consistent performance in the analysis of rodent ECGs, particularly for global and short-term HRV metrics, showing promise as a resource for preclinical research.

Among its strengths, the tool integrates statistical calculations and graphical representations, such as histograms and Poincaré diagrams, which offer complementary insights into HRV patterns and can aid in data interpretation. Despite these advances, some limitations were identified, including discrepancies observed in the NN20, pNN20, NN6, and pNN6 parameters, as well as the lack of reference values for these indices in rodents.

For future perspectives, it is proposed to refine the algorithm and expand the database with different experimental rodent profiles. Additionally, considering that HRV reflects aspects of autonomic modulation, the tool could be applied in studies aimed at understanding interactions between the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Mariana da Palma Valério: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Terigi Augusto Scardovelli: Methodology, Software, Validation.

Vlasta Bari: Visualization.

Pietra Aguiar dos Reis: Writing – original draft.

Silvia Becker: Software.

Axel Loewe: Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

Silvia Cristina Martini: Data curation.

Silvia Regina Matos da Silva Boschi: Visualization, Investigation.

Tabajara de Oliveira Gonzalez: Writing – review and editing.

Alessandro Pereira da Silva: Writing – original draft, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Tool name

Select ECG tool

Parameter configuration

Sample rate

Filters

Send file

Time Domain Analysis

Graphic

Result of cardiac
variability parameters

Statistical Analysis

Poincaré plot

Histogram plot

Filtered signal

R Detection

Preprint not peer reviewed

A

BPC - ECG

BY MARIANA DA PALMA VALERIO

**BLOOD
PRESSURE**

ELECTROCARDIOGRAM

B

SETTINGS

SAMPLE RATE

HIGH PASS FILTER

LOW PASS FILTER

NOTCH PASS FILTER

SELECT FILE IN EXCEL

i

C

TIME DOMAIN ANALYSIS

Amplitude (Hz)

Time (ms)

- RAW DATA
- FILTERED DATA
- PEAK R MARKING

dadorato1.10.xlsx

Heart rate: 394.79 bpm

Average: 151.96 ms

NNZ0: 2

NN6: 15

SDNN: 2.38 ms

rMSSD: 3.29 ms

pNNZ0: 0.26 %

pNN6: 1.98 %

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

i

D

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Poincaré plot

Histogram plot

i

Distribution of Values by Reference Range (%)

